

COGNITIVE-LINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF INTERPRETATION

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The article scrutinizes cognitive-linguistic aspects of interpretation and translation process. This is explained within the types of this profession. Language systems with their challenges were analyzed from psychological aspect, as well. As a verbal sign, three types of translations have been classified in the study which are interlingual, intralingual and intersemiotic. Analyzing the topic, it turns out that translation is seen as a language of sign. Consecutive, simultaneous, sight translations have been compared from linguistic perspectives respectively.

Keywords: sight translation, interpretation, consecutive, simultaneous, sign language.

There are two major characteristics of interpretation. The first one is the rendering of live in the source language to live utterances in target language. The source language is considered to be the speaker's language while the target language is regarded the language of receiver of translation. Interpretation importantly includes one of three dyads:

- 1) spoken source language (SSL) and spoken target language (STL)
- 2) spoken source language and signed target language
- 3) signed source language and signed target language.

Secondly, interpretation has the immediacy characteristic. It means that interpreter should process speech and translate it simultaneously or consecutively into another language without leaving the chance to other alternative renderings.

In simultaneous translation, the person speaks or signs in the native language and interpreter translates loudly or signs what is told in the target language [1]. The interpreter should comprehend the next message in the source language. This is a complicated process. Interpreters differ in their delay between speeches or discussion of the information. Interpreter receives the message, then produces and makes a conversion simultaneously. Simultaneous translation demonstrates cognitive and linguistic challenges under certain conditions. There is a big time delay between the produced utterance and rendered interpreting. These hardships are not found only in oral interpretation but also in sight translation. In any case, the quality of simultaneous translation would be high if the interpreter found access to the text prior to actual event.

In medical translation such an opportunity may be impossible, hence the speed of simultaneous translation might slow down in order to make information more accurate. Another type of interpretation which is called consecutive interpretation, the speaker produces a brief speech including one more sentences and then make pauses while the interpreter translates the information into the target language. Once the interpretation is over, the speaker produces the next sentences in the source language. For example, panic attack is a psychological disease which needs to be treated as well. [PAUSE] Its major symptoms are as follows [PAUSE]: the patient feels like dying or passing out, he/she cannot sleep at nights with the fear of dying or going mad [PAUSE].

So such patients suffer from insomnia and anxiety all day long. [PAUZE] The most effective drug to cure the disease is alprazolam. Along with advantages, it also has some side effects such as nausea, dizziness [PAUSE].

As seen from the above mentioned example, there are some pauses made by the speaker and interpreter. They should wait for each other to complete their speeches. Otherwise, the information given to the audience would be very obscure or misunderstood by the audience.

Consecutive interpretation must be more precise than simultaneous interpreting since it gives the translator more time lapse to find a more appropriate conversion and does not have the problem of the burden of listening and translating simultaneously like in simultaneous interpretation. Compared to simultaneous translation, consecutive translation is more time-consuming since both sides should wait for the interpretation to be completed prior to starting the next "information".

Translation requires movement between the written forms of both languages. We can also find translations between sign languages. It is crucial to emphasize that sign language is comprehensive. The vital characteristic feature of translation is that it is inclined not to be live. As mentioned above, it involves more time lapse between the source language and rendering into the target language. Time lapse gives the chance to consider alternative translations, study into previous translations, help from machine translators by laptop or computer [16].

Materials are not different so they are the same both for translation and interpretation. Since it offers a chance to take the input and output provided into account. Because the target production is isolated in time from the source material [17].

Youdelman says: "The most qualified translators are those who write well in their native language and who have mastered punctuation, spelling and grammar. Translators know how to analyze a text and are keenly aware of the fact that translation does not mean word-for-word replacement, but that context is the bottom line for an accurate rendition of any text". The most skilled translators realize the details and connotative power of two tongues and understand the level of the diction which is relevant to the audience [13].

Sight translation is the rendering of a written document orally [6]. An interpreter reads the written information in the source language, then he/she interprets it into the target language. In a medical conference, the interpreter is given a document at the moment of interpretation. Documents may be different in length and the interpreter does not have a chance to review them prior to interpretation. Interpreters had better look through the documents quickly in order to get acquainted with the theme of the translation. Since there are some contractions and acronyms which the interpreter should identify or learn their codes. It is a usual case for an interpreter not be aware of such information. Translation without acquaintance may work out with the documents which are clear and brief. The more complex documents should be reviewed before being given to translators. One of the challenges related to sight translation is that this kind of translation requires interpreter to read and speak in two tongues simultaneously. There may be a threat to clarity and accuracy of speech that would induce misunderstanding for the audience [5].

Signed language interpretation and oral interpretation are nearly the same except the channel of signals. For example, American sign language may completely discuss any scientific topic which is found in English.

First distinction in interpretation between a signed and spoken languages and interpretation between two spoken languages are inclined to be practical. Interpretation of an English speech into signed language can be more time-consuming than the equivalent spoken language, particularly if there is a lot of technical words.

The matters of language access and efficient interaction are more complicated and need more attention than what happens when individuals say that they need to find somebody to translate the information or get somebody who knows French or Italian. Communication is considered to be very complex. For example, when the doctor cannot converse in the language that the patient know, communication will be awful and it may have a negative impact on the patient. Without foreign language knowledge, vital data and gestures may be misunderstood and lost as a result. In this case the importance of an interpreter or translator is big. Via interpretation the doctor and patient will be able to understand each other very well. Correct information transferred via interpreters may change someone's life.

Translation studies usually involve two texts with one meaning. These are target language text and source language text. However, the reader of the translated texts is aware of only the target language text. There are a number of reasons listed in translation studies which include the distinctions between the target language text and source language text [15]. Some varieties are the outcome of differences between the target and source cultures and the standards of target and source literature. While teaching translation techniques and strategies available to the interpreter to tackle such hardships are introduced [14].

The article aims to analyze the linguistic aspects of interpretation, especially academic and literary texts from the field of humanities [3]. Linguistic aspects of

translation are viewed with regard to translation practice, translation theory, translation theory and target language readers [2].

Language systems and translation include the following challenges;

1. problems in pronunciation which is concerned with how the word is pronounced.

2. challenges with lexicology that consists of nonsense texts, derived and composed neologisms, different word formation patterns between languages.

3. problems with grammatical structures including grammatical categories such as plurality, tenses, gender.

4. troubles with syntax which deals with pragmatic relationships, the affect of word order such as tense agreement

5. problems with semantics which encompasses semantic range and polysemy

6. difficulties with non-standard varieties and styles

We classify 3 types of translation as a verbal sign which have been given below;

1. Intralingual

2. Interlingual

3. Intersemiotic

The first one is sometimes called as rewording which is an interpretation of verbal signs through other signs of the same tongue.

The second one is also named as translation proper that means verbal signs a translation via some other languages.

And the last one which is also called transmutation is the translation of verbal signs through the signs of non-verbal sign construction.

Intralingual interpretation of words uses synonymous words. But the synonymy does not mean full parity. A word or an idiomatic phrase-word can be completely translated only via an equivalent combination of code-units [12].

Similarly, at the level of interlingual translation, there is merely no complete parity between two code-units whereas messages might function as relevant translations of foreign code-units.

Interpretation from one language into another replaces information in one language, not separate code-units but for all messages in some other languages. Such an interpretation is regarded as a reported speech. The interpreter recodes and transmits that was received from another source.

Functional grammar approach to linguistics is concentrated on the aim and usage of language and checks oral and written languages in the context of their usage. The links between words employed and the senses derived are not considered as arbitrary. "Rather language is determined as being functional whereby the meaning is created though the choice of words and the syntactic structure through which the words are produced" [10]. Hence, the study of language from functional point of view and as the study of translation of language can't be separated from the situations where language use occurs.

Interpreter education has required a comprehensive research with linguistic rules and practice since the

2nd half of XX century. For this reason, linguistic courses including pragmatics, discourse analysis and linguistic philosophy are very important at the interpretation departments. Such courses lead to the development of students' different skills. Interpretation, as a multi-branched field, is also closely related with psychology, sociology, computer sciences, information technologies. Structural, stylistic, semiotic and semantic linguistic analysis of interpretation demonstrate that the study of interpretation is not only a linguistic practice but also a reflection of practice in the cognitive and socio-cultural aspects of linguistics.

In the research works conducted by Nida and Catford, the target is to adopt the linguistic features of translation, particularly at the level of text. In this regard, the attention is drawn to text to which linguistic tools function [8]. But such endeavours did not gain success. Hatim and Mason are of a common opinion to process text during the course of translation to illustrate the importance of discourse, pragmatics and the context. [11]

"Manipulation school" founded by Toury, Vermeer and Herman may be considered to be starting point of contemporary interpretation theory that uses linguistics as a means to realize the socio-cultural aspects operating externally but still affecting the main character of translation straightly.

Similarly, Holmes paid attention to a more relational and functional concept of equivalence where text is accepted as a reflection of historical and socio-cultural rules.

Although context, text and other communicative-functional approach assisted to gain success in interpretation and translation at the end of 1990s, the impact of cognitive Linguistics went on to stress the main role of human comprehension and perception for higher successes in translation studies. This approach allowed scientists and researchers to not only pay attention to text or speech, but also on the researchers' background which covers different worldwide issues. The translator's or interpreter's ideas, comprehension of the environment and the globe around them, a worldly- structured socio-cultural competence [4], psychological and physiological aspects of their human character loaded with different cognitive-linguistic theories should be melted in the same pot to characterize a perfect researcher in this field [10].

For this reason, it might be said that linguistic aspect of interpretation must be learnt with regard to translation and interpretation first of all. With this aim, a number of skills and capabilities should be obtained one by one in order to realize well what qualities a translation and interpretation should own from linguistic point of view. The reflections of linguistic theory on the translation/interpretation work assist us to illustrate the multidisciplinary character of translation studies and psycho-cognitive features of interpretation and translation [7].

References

1. ALISOY, H. A DISCUSSION OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION, ITS CHALLENGES AND DIFFICULTIES WITH ITS IMPLEMENTATION. ZNANSTVENA MISEL Учредители: Global Science Center LP, (65), 40-42.
2. Babayev Javid. Grammatical aspects of translation in English and Azerbaijani. Publisher.agency: Proceedings of the 4th International Scientific Conference «Research Retrieval and Academic Letters» (December 7-8, 2023). Warsaw, Poland, 2023. 362p
3. Babayev Javid Sabir. Linguistic and cultural aspects of simultaneous translation. Publisher.agency: Proceedings of the 4th International Scientific Conference «Progress in Science» (November 9-10, 2023). Brussels, Belgium, 2023. 229p
4. Babayev Javid. Impact of socio-linguistic and socio-cultural factors on translation process. Sciences of Europe. № 128, Praha, Czech Republic, 2023
5. Babayev Javid. Requirements for simultaneous interpretation. Publisher.agency: Proceedings of the 5th International Scientific Conference «Foundations and Trends in Research» (February 8-9, 2024). Copenhagen, Denmark, 2024. 168p
6. Babayev Javid. Significance of language skills and language aspects in sight translation. Danish scientific journal. Vol.1, № 77, 2023
7. Javid Babayev. Cognitive aspects of simultaneous and consecutive interpretations. Proceedings of the 1st International Scientific Conference «Interdisciplinary Science Studies» (January 19-20, 2023). Dublin, Ireland, 2023. 144p
8. Javid Babayev. Different theoretical approaches to translation process. Publisher.agency: Proceedings of the 5th International Scientific Conference «Theoretical Hypotheses and Empirical results» (December 14-15, 2023). Oslo, Norway, 2023. 393p
9. Bell, R. T. (1998). Psychological/cognitive approaches. In M. Baker (Ed), Routledge encyclopedia of translation studies. London & New York: Routledge.
10. Gerot&Wignell (1995) Making sense of functional grammar: an introductory workbook, Publisher, Antipodean Educational Enterprises, 1995, p.258 p.
11. Hatim, B& Ian, M. (1997). The translator as a communicator. London, UK: Routledge.
12. Loescher, W. (1991). Translation performance, translation process and translation strategies. Tuebingen: Guten Narr.
13. Newmark, P. (1988b). Approaches to Translation. Hertfordshire: Prentice Hall.
14. Nida, E. A. (1964). Towards a science of translation, with special reference to principles and procedures involved in Bible translating. Leiden: Brill.
15. Seguinot, C. (1989). The translation process. Toronto: H.G. Publications.
16. Venuti, L. (1998). Strategies of translation. In M. Baker (Ed.), Encyclopedia of translation studies (pp. 240-244). London and New York: Routledge.
17. Zhongying, F. (1994). An applied theory of translation. Beijing: Foreign Languages Teaching & Research Press.